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INTERPERSONAL RELATIONSHIP IN WELL-BEING OF GYMNAST ATHLETES

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Abstract

Gymnastics can be challenging and even unsafe and stressful related to intense pressure to succeed, and embarrassment of poor performance in a competition (White & Bennie, 2015). A lot of studies have been argued that these are opportunities to develop psychological skills and characteristics that can be translated into behaviors that may be useful throughout the athlete's lifetime (White & Bennie, 2015). For example, gymnastics can aid in the development of coping strategies, to manage stress occurred the games (Thelwell, Such, Wetson, Such & Greenlees, 2010). White and colleagues (2015) found that because gymnasts perform in competitions at a young age, they subsequently develop self-confidence as a result of being exposed to and handling this unique pressure, and they concluded that the athletic atmosphere, the relationships between the athletes, coaches and peers, along with the coaching styles they experience, have been shown to influence the progression of the athlete's self-efficacy and resilience (White & Bennie, 2015).

In the article, interpersonal relations are analyzed as one of the factors that determine the success of gymnasts, and the ideas and thoughts existing in the scientific and psychological literature in this direction are systematized. As it is known, events occurring in the environment, as well as the behavior of people around them, affect gymnasts. These factors can manifest themselves in both positive and negative directions. It is true that one issue should be kept in mind here that although this does not affect the behavior of elite athletes, it directly affects the results of inexperienced athletes who have just started gymnastics. It is noted that, in addition to the mentioned, it has an important influence on this process in family relations. Establishing interpersonal relations in the family in the right direction has a positive effect on both the moral and psychological state of the athlete, as well as on his interactions with teammates. The presence of family relationships, the sincere attitude of parents to their children and their support in this way, of course, have a positive effect on both the personality qualities of athletes and the results of competitions. One of the factors that have an important influence on the social psychological preparation of gymnasts is the coach-athlete relationship.

Keywords: Gymnast, sport, personality, interaction, motivation, success, team, interpersonal relations

The psychological aspects of sport, and training athletes is one of the urgent problems of the modern era. However, unfortunately, some simplistic ideas still prevail in this field, and there are still ideas focused only on the fact that physical training ensures sports success. It should be taken into account that psychological preparation cannot be taken only as a factor that ensures successful participation in sports competitions. Of course, psychological factors are most often manifested in competitions, but the role of psychology in sports is not limited only to the lack of sufficient psychological preparation to participate in them.

In recent years, there has been a sharp increase in attention to the information processes that determine the personal qualities of athletes and coaches, collective interaction, building teams, and studying the nature of interpersonal relationships that exist between them (White & Bennie, 2015; Hessel, Hocking & Davies, 2010; Yang, Schaefer, Zhang, Covassin, Ding & Heiden, 2014).

Growing research highlights the prevalence of the psychological effects athletes experience throughout their collegiate athletic careers and also emphasizes the role athletic trainers play in the daily care of athletes. Thus, it is important to examine the athletic trainers

viewpoint on the psychological aspect of sport participation (Yang et al., 2014).

Sports psychology is responsible for scientific-methodical development of all issues related to the organization of the training-training process as a whole and preparation for competitions, education and training of the athlete.

Achieving success in the technical, physical and tactical training of athletes is possible only by having the right influence on the psyche of the athletes. It is impossible to train athletes successfully without being based on the psychology of the individual and the team. This is especially important in the field of gymnastics.

Sometimes young athletes who have not formed their character, whose stable moral and willful qualities have not been fully educated are engaged in this type of sport. Young gymnasts have great motor abilities and personal qualities are not enough for their manifestation. It is important to strengthen the training process of young gymnasts, properly organize the formation of necessary resources, control them and prepare them for collective action.

In different countries athlete trainers are required to take a formal psychology course and are taught to recognize the signs and symptoms often associated

with mental health disorders, eating disorders and other psychological symptoms such as stress, anger or anxiety, that they may meet while working with athletes (Roh & Perna, 2000). Trainers can support athletes in improving their mental health through the use of basic counseling skills and psychological strategies such as active listening, goal setting, motivation/team building, imagery, mental training, positive reinforcement, relaxation, and visualization (Taylor & Taylor, 1997).

Research shows that gymnasts' personality traits correspond to qualities identified in the five-factor personality questionnaire (Costa Jr, P. T., & McCrae, R. R. (1992); Skinner, N., & Brewer, N. (2004); Bhambri, E., Dhillon, P.K., & Sahni, S.P. (2005); Bali, I.S. Kon (1984), Mukhina V.S. (2000). According to some of the psychologists, the formation of personality qualities in sports activities, the athlete's greater success in competitions (Andreeva G. M. (2008); Kon I.S (1995); Ilin E.P. (2004); Kelishev I.G. (1972); Y.Y. Palaima, B. J. Cretti (2012). Researchers studying the main motives for doing sports (Melnikov M.V. (1987); Dimitrienkova L.P. (1980); Volkov I.P. (2002), Dmitrichenko L.P. (1980.); Singer R.H. (1980); Rodionov A.V. (2004) ; Rudik P.A. (1964); Stanbulova N.V.(2005); R.S. Uyenberg P.S. (2005)) show that it is difficult to specify which motive acts as a success motive in gymnasts. In addition to all this, in Azerbaijan researchers and psychologists have studied special aspect of sports psychology (E. Huseyunov, E. Abbasov, E. Aliyev, etc.). However, it is difficult to say that systematic research has been conducted in this field. In this case these facts make it necessary to study the problem in finer details.

Method: The main aim of this study is to determine the role of interpersonal relations in the social psychological training of gymnasts, to clarify the factors that have a fundamental influence on their success. The aim of the study was examined using literature analyzing and descriptive research method.

Literature review: According to studies it should be noted that when talking about the social and psychological preparation of gymnasts, it is necessary to pay attention to interpersonal relations. At this age, one of the reasons for the adolescent crisis and conflicts with others is the desire for a certain independence, the increase in pride and resentment, which manifests itself more in the behavior of adolescents. An increase in critical attitude towards adults, a sharp reaction to the attempts of others to demean their dignity, to underestimate their maturity and potential opportunities often lead to the emergence of conflicts during adolescence. "Peer orientation often manifests itself in the fear of rejection by peers. The emotional well-being of a person increasingly depends on his place in the collective, it is determined primarily by the attitude and values of his friends (Muchina V., 2000).

I. S. Kon considers the main psychological mastery of this stage of ontogenesis to be the discovery of one's own inner world, the realization of one's uniqueness and unlike others. This discovery is directly related to the isolation of personality and is experienced by teenagers as a value (Kon, I.S., 1984). In this regard, the system of interpersonal relations of each gymnast

determines the characteristics of relations in the group. Active acquisition of communication skills begins after the gymnast joins the group. The formation of his personality in the system of personal relations depends on the establishment of relations with his peers, the position of the gymnast or his status in the group. The absence of problems in interpersonal relations is one of the most important conditions for the unity and efficiency of a group of gymnasts (Andreeva Q, 1999). Compliance assessment criteria: results of joint activity; emotional balance of activity participants and participants' satisfaction with this activity.

It is known that the level of interpersonal relations of gymnasts is determined both by the similarity of some qualities of group members and by the difference in others. As a result, this leads to complementarity in joint problem solving. Note that a specific group of gymnasts represents a certain completeness. The levels of interpersonal relations in these groups depend on socio-psychological, psychological and psychophysiological characteristics. Similarity at all levels manifests itself in interpersonal relationships. When interpersonal relationships are broken, that is, when people do not understand each other, do not want to and cannot communicate, it causes the emergence of social and psychological barriers between gymnasts, which shows itself in the results of gymnasts.

Types of communicative behavior have a great influence on the nature of interpersonal relations of people in gymnastics groups: individuals who aspire to leadership, who can solve problems only by subordinating other members of the group; individuals trying to solve the problem on their own; adapt to the group (conformists), easily obey the orders of its other members; It is possible to refer to collectives trying to solve problems with joint efforts. From this point of view, those gymnasts take the initiative themselves, as well as accepting the suggestions of other members of the group. According to this approach, behavior is largely determined by the situation or environment. In other words, the influence and reinforcement of the environment determines the behavioral pattern of gymnasts. With the significant influence of the environment, the role of the gymnast's personality traits will be minimal. For example, if you are an introverted shy person, you may still act aggressive or even aggressive if someone attacks you. Many gymnasts are gentle and quiet people outside the competition arena, but the game (situation) requires them to be aggressive.

A qualitative study conducted by Theberge (2008) used interviews of both male and female athletes from various sports to further explore their accounts of the relationship between their health and sport participation.

Theberge (2008) found that participants controlled health threats through separating their physical health and their immediate ability to compete in their sport. Therefore, it is recommended that coaches and healthcare professionals inform and spread awareness of athletes' well-being and the negative consequences that could result from injuries later in life (Theberge, 2008).

The author mentioned that although it was recognized and accepted the risks associated with athletics, athletes reported both physical and psychological benefits of sport participation (Theberge, 2008). As it was mentioned, trainers are obligated to provide services that they are knowledgeable in and therefore should use to treat athletes. Roh and colleagues highlighted that part of professional responsibility of the trainers is to stay informed of newly established research and strategies addressing psychological distress (Roh & Perna, 2000). It would be beneficial for them to be trained to recognize, evaluate, and work with athletes who may experience psychological symptoms (Roh & Perna, 2000).

It should be noted that a different feature of sports compared to many other types of activities is that sports are always an activity that requires overcoming certain difficulties. Therefore, education of the athlete's qualities is an organic part of his social psychological preparation. Purposefulness, discipline, confidence, initiative, independence, courage (courage), perseverance (stubbornness), determination, self-control in the interpersonal relationships of gymnasts, qualities such as endurance have a significant effect (Khorni K., 1993).

The presence of psychological stability in interpersonal relationships is of great practical importance. Because stability protects a person from fragmentation and personality disorders, creates a foundation for internal harmony, mental health and high performance. Disintegration of the personality means the loss of the organizing role of the highest level of the psyche in the regulation of behavior and activity, the collapse of the hierarchy of life meanings, values, motives, and goals. The presence of psychological stability in interpersonal relationships directly determines the vitality, mental and somatic health of gymnasts. Psychological stability is a complex and comprehensive human quality. It combines a wide range of multi-level events.

In interpersonal relations, three aspects of psychological stability come to the fore: firmness, stability; balance, the ability to maintain a constant mood and activity level, to be sensitive to different aspects of life, to have different interests, to avoid simplification in values, goals and desires can also be considered as an important component of psychological stability in interpersonal relationships.

Finally, on the one hand, the development of constant interpersonal interaction and, as a result, involvement in many social relationships, and on the other hand, resistance to excessively strong interaction, causes contradictions in the athlete's behavior and interpersonal relationships. The latter can violate the necessary personal autonomy, form of behavior, goal and activity style, independence in choosing. This prevents the gymnast from analyzing herself, following the direction, and building her life path. In other words, it includes the ability to achieve and maintain psychological stability in interpersonal relationships. In this regard, psychological stability in interpersonal relationships requires the ability to resist external influences by following one's intentions and goals.

Thus, the emergence of psychological stability in interpersonal relationships is a positive image of the

gymnast, which, in turn, increases the role of a person as a positive group personality. At the same time, stability in interpersonal relations leads to a decrease in conflicts in interpersonal relations and an increase in competition results.

One of the main issues in the research conducted in this direction is related to the study of which factors influence the behavior of gymnasts. In these studies, it is specifically noted that physiological and psychological factors affect the behavior of gymnasts and thus their performance. In those studies, psychological factors are mostly divided into two groups. The first group can be attributed to the persistent personality traits of gymnasts. Because without these features, it is actually impossible for gymnasts to succeed in a certain competition. The second group is related to the characteristics of psychological reactions during extreme situations. For example, being anxious in various situations can be characterized as a personality trait. However, the manifestation of anxiety in gymnasts before performing a complex movement for the first time without the help of a coach is more situational. At this time, of course, not personality traits, but the situation is the dominant factor.

Empirical facts show that the emergence of differences in personality characteristics of athletes depends primarily on the type of sport, skill level, competition level, gender and cultural factors. Thus, a single personality and its characteristics cannot be considered as the only factor influencing the behavior and performance of gymnasts in different situations. In order to properly understand the content of all these issues, the whole complex of factors contributing to this process should be clarified. In this regard, in addition to the personality of the gymnasts, the analysis of data related to the current conditions, the gymnast's personality and the interaction of the current conditions allows better prediction of the gymnast's performance.

Here, selected and effective psychological characteristics are determined according to gymnasts' competition experience. Compared to weaker or inexperienced gymnasts, elite gymnasts have high self-confidence. They are less worried during the competition, clearly focus on the given task. They can find a way out of difficult situations. Intrinsic motivation is at a high level, and even in the event of failure on the competition field, it is often attributed to external sharia. In contrast, symptoms such as low self-confidence, high anxiety, focusing on distractions, inability to cope with difficult situations, external motivation or seeing the cause of failures in oneself are more common in inexperienced or weak gymnasts. When a gymnast steps out onto the competition floor to perform certain exercises, her movements look quite fluid and easy from the outside, but in reality they are quite complex. In this regard, in order to perform a certain complex action accurately and safely, it is necessary to integrate the information received from different sensor systems. Therefore, the higher the gymnast's level of experience, the more likely he is to adjust his movements directly based on environmental information. At this time, his motor movements are significantly dependent on the received sensory input. However, given the complexity

and dynamic nature of gymnastic skills, it is important to note that a gymnast's performance may vary from practice to practice and competition to competition. At this time, it can cause changes in the psychological conditions of gymnasts due to the influence of the environment. This, in turn, has a negative effect on the gymnasts' results during the competition.

A number of researchers believe that the emergence of dramatic changes in psychological states is one of the potential preconditions for the occurrence of movement errors and injuries in gymnasts. In such conditions, at the same time, there are cases of sudden loss of existing skills. Gymnasts suffering from such a "lost skill syndrome" are unable to perform a certain movement that was previously performed automatically. This loss of skill can have significant consequences for gymnasts' performance. For example, most gymnasts experience intense stress when trying to perform a "lost" skill. This, in turn, leads to their complete avoidance of performing those skills or impaired motor control.

Weise and colleagues (1991) examined trainers' use of psychological strategies when treating athletes throughout the recovery process after any injuries. Participants rated their perception of the significance and usefulness of psychosocial strategies which they are taught to use in the clinical setting. It was concluded that specific and individualized programs should be designed to treat athletes who experience psychological symptoms (Weise et al., 1991).

According to literature it is obvious that effective communication techniques are beneficial to convey information and provide motivational feedback. A team approach to rehabilitation was recommended to provide holistic care for the athlete (Weise et al. (1991).

Conclusion: According to literature the following items were concluded:

- The use of different methods of managing situational anxiety in gymnasts plays an important role in the special psychological preparation of gymnasts;
- Peer interpersonal relationships of gymnasts can both encourage and hinder the development of motivation in their sports activities;
- Unfavorable mutual relations with reference groups increase psychological tension in gymnasts and lead to a decrease in motivation in performing various gymnastic tasks;
- In order to increase the social psychological preparation of gymnasts in competitions, it is necessary to develop social psychological intervention programs. Such programs enable them to adapt to the environment while correctly evaluating their psychological qualities;

- Psychological factors play an important role in a gymnast's failure in any competition. Therefore, in their work, coaches should pay special attention to the social and psychological preparation of gymnasts in addition to tactical and technical training.

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